

FIBER (YARN)-MATRIX INTERFACIAL STRESS ANALYSIS BY USING THE HETEROGENEOUS ELEMENT METHOD

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SUMMARY: In this paper a heterogeneous element, a new numerical tool, is developed for fiber-matrix interfacial stress analysis. There are several advantages gained using the heterogeneous element. First, a heterogeneous element can contain one or more kinds of materials with different moduli and other mechanical properties. Therefore, it is not necessary to match element boundaries to fiber-matrix interfaces. This turns mesh generation into a simple process. More important, the formulation of a heterogeneous element guarantees that both the equilibrium conditions and the continuity of displacement at the interface are satisfied. Yet, it allows for the stress and strain jump at the interface. Because the formulation reflects the actual physical situation at the interface, calculated interfacial stress becomes rapidly convergent to an accurate result as the element mesh becomes finer.

KEYWORDS: interfacial stress, finite element analysis, heterogeneous materials, fibers, yarns, micro-mechanics, meso-mechanics

INTRODUCTION

Micro-failure often emanates from the yarn (fiber)-matrix interface. It can be caused by interfacial stress concentration or interfacial debond. Therefore, it is important to predict interfacial stress concentration. Many attempts have been undertaken by using the conventional finite element approach. However, there have been two great difficulties[1-6]:

1. The modulus of the fibers (or yarns) could be 50-100 times higher than that of the matrix. Serious stress concentration along the yarn-matrix and fiber-matrix interface therefore exists. It is important to predict this interfacial stress concentration. Use of conventional iso-parametrical displacement element can not satisfy the equilibrium conditions along the interface. It thus provides poor prediction performance of interfacial stress concentration. Significant error may occur even with employment of a fine mesh. A commonly considered way to improve the convergent rate of stress is to employ mixed or hybrid finite element method, as it is possible to construct compatible stress functions. However, due to the huge

difference of moduli between fibers and matrix, there is a tangential stress jump at the interface between the two materials. The element, based upon a compatible stress function, may be unable to converge to the actual stress at the interface because of its failure to model the stress jump.

2. Because of the complexity of the composite microstructure, it is very difficult to match element boundaries to the interfaces of fibers, yarns and matrix. Recently, many textile composites have been developed, such as 2-D and 3-D woven, braided and knitted composites. Their microstructures are more difficult to model. For example, Fig.1 is the yarn structure of a three-dimensional braided unit cell. Because the micro-geometry of the cross section varies from cross-section to cross-section, mesh generation is a time consuming, tedious task.

Fig.1: The microstructure of 3-D braided composite unit cell

In this paper, a new heterogeneous element is developed for interfacial stress analysis. This new finite element model provides two advantages:

1. The formulation of heterogeneous finite element guarantees that both the equilibrium conditions and the continuity of displacement at the interface are satisfied. Yet, it allows for discontinuity of stress and strain at the interface. Because of these two characteristics, the element model reflects the actual physical situation. As such, calculated interfacial stress becomes rapidly convergent to an accurate result as the element mesh becomes finer.
2. A heterogeneous element can consist of one or more materials with different moduli and other mechanical properties. It is not necessary to match element boundaries to fiber (or yarn) –matrix interfaces. Therefore, the complexity of the composite microstructure does not create difficulties for mesh generation.

The heterogeneous element can be formulated as displacement elements or mixed elements. In this paper, a 2-D six-node heterogeneous displacement element is formulated. The heterogeneous finite element method is employed to calculate the interfacial stress of a dissimilar plate and a unidirectional fibrous composite. Two numerical examples are given. The initial study has shown that the heterogeneous element method is an effective tool for the prediction of interfacial stress.

FORMULATION OF 2-DHETEROGENEOUS ELEMENT

Basic principles

Fig.2. is an illustration of the heterogeneous finite element. The element contains two materials: material 1 and material 2. Material 1 has a modulus of E_1 and a Poisson ratio of ν_1 ; material 2 has a modulus of E_2 and a Poisson ratio of ν_2 . The mathematical expression of the interface between the two materials is $F(x,y) = 0$. The displacement field in material 1 is defined by $\{U^I(x,y), V^I(x,y)\}$ and the displacement field in material 2 is defined by $\{U^{II}(x,y), V^{II}(x,y)\}$. U denotes the displacement in x -direction and V denotes the displacement in y -direction. In order to construct a fast convergent element, the mathematical model has to reflect the physical reality at the interface. The physical reality at the interface includes:

- a. continuity of displacement at the interface,
(See Fig.2, $\{U^I(x,y), V^I(x,y)\} = \{U^{II}(x,y), V^{II}(x,y)\}$ along the interface.)
- b. discontinuity of normal strains(ϵ_n), shear strains(τ_{nt}) and tangential stress (σ_t) at the interface, and
- c. equilibrium conditions, i.e. continuity of normal stress and shear stress ($\sigma_n^I = \sigma_n^{II}$, $\tau_{nt}^I = \tau_{nt}^{II}$) at the interface.

Where σ denotes normal stress, τ denotes shear stress, ϵ denotes strain, and subscripts n and t denote normal direction and tangential direction of the interface of two materials, respectively. In order to satisfy the above three conditions, the formulation of the displacement function must follow the following three basic principles:

- a. Displacement function must be continuous along the interface between two dissimilar materials.
- b. Discontinuity of the first derivatives of the displacement function must be allowed in order to reflect possible stress and strain jump at the interface.
- c. Interfacial normal stress and interfacial shear stress must be in equilibrium.

2-a Heterogeneous element

2-b Interfacial conditions

Fig.2: The illustration of the heterogeneous element

Formulation of the Two-Dimensional Heterogeneous Element

Based upon the three aforementioned principles, the 2-D heterogeneous element can be formulated.

See Fig.2. Let the displacement functions in material I be U^I and V^I , and in material 2 be U^{II} and V^{II} . The boundary between these two materials is $F(x,y) = 0$. Let U^I , V^I , U^{II} and V^{II} be

$$\begin{aligned} U^I(x,y) &= U^0(x,y) - h_u(x,y)F(x,y) \\ V^I(x,y) &= V^0(x,y) - h_v(x,y)F(x,y) \\ U^{II}(x,y) &= U^0(x,y) + h_u(x,y)F(x,y) \\ V^{II}(x,y) &= V^0(x,y) + h_v(x,y)F(x,y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

respectively.

Because $F(x,y) = 0$ at the interface, $U^I(x,y) = U^{II}(x,y) = U^0(x,y)$ and $V^I(x,y) = V^{II}(x,y) = V^0(x,y)$ at the interface. Therefore, the first principle mentioned in the last subsection is satisfied. If the derivatives of the second terms on the right side of the above equations do not equal zero, the derivatives of displacement will not be continuous. The discontinuity allows for a possible stress and strain jump at the interface. Therefore the second principle has also be satisfied.

$H_u(x,y)$ and $h_v(x,y)$ can be determined by the equilibrium conditions

$\sigma_n^I = \sigma_n^{II}$, $\tau_{nt}^I = \tau_{nt}^{II}$ on the interface $F(x,y) = 0$. After a mathematical manipulation, one can prove that equilibrium conditions can be satisfied if $h_u(x,y)$ and $h_v(x,y)$ satisfy the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} (h_u F_x + h_v F_y) &= \frac{1}{(F_y^2 + F_x^2)} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{E_1}{1-\nu_1^2} + \frac{E_2}{1-\nu_2^2} \right)} \\ &\bullet \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{E_1}{1-\nu_1^2} - \frac{E_2}{1-\nu_2^2} \right) \left[\frac{\partial U^0}{\partial x} F_x^2 + \frac{\partial V^0}{\partial y} F_y^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U^0}{\partial y} \right) F_y F_x \right] \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{E_1 \nu_1}{1-\nu_1^2} - \frac{E_2 \nu_2}{1-\nu_2^2} \right) \left[\frac{\partial U^0}{\partial x} F_y^2 + \frac{\partial V^0}{\partial y} F_x^2 - \left(\frac{\partial V^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U^0}{\partial y} \right) F_y F_x \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (h_v F_x - h_u F_y) &= \frac{1}{(F_y^2 + F_x^2)} \frac{(G_1 - G_2)}{(G_1 + G_2)} \bullet \\ &\left\{ \left(\frac{\partial V^0}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial U^0}{\partial x} \right) (2F_y F_x) + \left(\frac{\partial U^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial V^0}{\partial x} \right) (F_y^2 - F_x^2) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

where F_x and F_y denote the partial derivatives of $F(x,y)$ with respect to x and y , respectively; G_1 and G_2 are the shear moduli of material 1 and material 2, respectively.

Once displacement functions U^0 and V^0 are defined, $h_u(x,y)$ and $h_v(x,y)$ can be solved from Eqs.(2). Thus, $\{U^I, V^I\}$ and $\{U^{II}, V^{II}\}$ can be defined and the displacement field can be determined. The following is an example for a six –node element.

Six-Node Element

Fig.3 is an illustration of a six-node element. It is assumed that the interface between the two materials is a straight line $Ax + By = C$

Fig.3: Six-node element

Let displacement in the element be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U^I &= a_u + b_u x + c_u y + d_u x^2 + e_u xy + f_u y^2 - h_u(x, y)(Ax + By - C) \\
 U^{II} &= a_u + b_u x + c_u y + d_u x^2 + e_u xy + f_u y^2 + h_u(x, y)(Ax + By - C) \\
 V^I &= a_v + b_v x + c_v y + d_v x^2 + e_v xy + f_v y^2 - h_v(x, y)(Ax + By - C) \\
 V^{II} &= a_v + b_v x + c_v y + d_v x^2 + e_v xy + f_v y^2 + h_v(x, y)(Ax + By - C)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Substituting the above equations into Eqs(2) and solving h_u and h_v , one can derive:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_x &= \frac{1}{(A^2 + B^2)^2} \left\{ (b_u + 2d_u x + e_u y)(C_E A^2 + (C_{Ev} + 2C_G)B^2)A \right. \\
 &+ (c_v + e_v x + 2f_v y)((C_E - 2C_G)B^2 + C_{Ev}A^2)A \\
 &+ (b_v + 2d_v x + e_v y + c_u + e_u x + 2f_u y)[(C_E - C_{Ev} - C_G)A^2 + C_G B^2]B \left. \right\} \\
 h_y &= \frac{1}{(A^2 + B^2)^2} \left\{ (b_u + 2d_u x + e_u y)((C_E - 2C_G)A^2 + C_{Ev}B^2)B \right. \\
 &+ (c_v + e_v x + 2f_v y)(C_E B^2 + (C_{Ev} + 2C_G)A^2)B \\
 &+ (b_v + 2d_v x + e_v y + c_u + e_u x + 2f_u y)[(C_E - C_{Ev} - C_G)B^2 + C_G A^2]A \left. \right\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Where

$$C_E = \frac{\frac{E_1}{1-\nu_1^2} - \frac{E_2}{1-\nu_2^2}}{\frac{E_1}{1-\nu_1^2} + \frac{E_2}{1-\nu_2^2}}, \quad C_{Ev} = \frac{\frac{E_1 \nu_1}{1-\nu_1^2} - \frac{E_2 \nu_2}{1-\nu_2^2}}{\frac{E_1}{1-\nu_1^2} + \frac{E_2}{1-\nu_2^2}}, \quad C_G = \frac{G_1 - G_2}{G_1 + G_2}$$

Substituting Eqs.(4) into Eqs.(3), displacement can be expressed in terms of $a_u, b_u, c_u, d_u, e_u, f_u, a_v, b_v, c_v, d_v, e_v, f_v$. It can be written in the matrix form as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U^I \\ V^I \\ U^{II} \\ V^{II} \end{Bmatrix} = [H] \{a_u \ a_v \ b_u \ b_v \ c_u \ c_v \ d_u \ d_v \ e_u \ e_v \ f_u \ f_v\}^T \quad (5)$$

where H is a 4x12 matrix. Its elements are functions of x and y . Substituting the node coordinates into equations (5), the nodal displacements u_i and v_i ($i=1,6$) can be expressed in terms of $a_u, b_u, c_u, d_u, e_u, f_u, a_v, b_v, c_v, d_v, e_v, f_v$. The inverse relationship allows us to express $a_u, b_u, c_u, d_u, e_u, f_u, a_v, b_v, c_v, d_v, e_v, f_v$ in terms of u_i and v_i ($i=1,6$). Substituting the relationship into Eq.(5), the displacement function can be written in terms of the nodal displacements u_i and v_i ($i=1, \dots, 6$):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U^I \\ U^{II} \\ V^I \\ V^{II} \end{Bmatrix} = [N] \{u_1 \ v_1 \ \dots \ u_6 \ v_6\} \quad (6)$$

This form is similar to the form of a displacement element. Thus, a procedure similar to one used in a conventional displacement element method can be used to derive the element and global stiffness matrices. At this point, nodal displacement can be calculated. Then, the element displacement field can be derived. Finally, the element stress and strain can be calculated.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Two numerical examples are analyzed using the heterogeneous element method. The first is shown in Fig.4-a. A plate is composed of two materials. The two materials have the same Poisson's ratio. The modulus of one material is 100 times of the other. The material properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for example 1

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Poisson ratio
1	200	0.3
2	2	0.3

The plate is simply supported on the lower boundary and the left boundary. A uniform distributed load is applied on the top boundary. Heterogeneous elements are used along the interface. The conventional iso-parametrical elements are employed for the remainder of the plate. Fig.4-b shows the distribution of σ_y along the right boundary, 4-c and 4-d show σ_y and τ_{xy} along the interface. Stress increases dramatically near the right edge of the interface. Results were compared with the conventional element method. A much finer element mesh is required for the conventional element method to achieve similar results.

4-a

4-b

4-c

4-a The uniform loaded dissimilar plate

4-b σ_y along the right side boundary

4-c σ_y along the interface

4-d

4-d τ_{xy} along the interface

Fig.4: The stress distribution calculated using the heterogeneous element method

The second example is shown in Fig.5-a. It is a unidirectional fibrous composite under a transverse load. The representative unit cell is shown in Fig.5-b. The composite is made from carbon fiber and epoxy resin. Material properties are listed in Table 2. Fig.5-c is the finite element mesh. The thick black line is the interface. The stress distribution along the lower interface is shown in Fig.6. The stress components σ_r and $\tau_{r\theta}$ are in equilibrium along the interface, i.e., these two stress components are continuous at the interface as shown in Fig.6-a. However, there is a stress jump of σ_θ , which has a different value on each side of the interface. Two stress curves are shown in Fig.6-b. One is the circumferential stress distribution on the matrix side and the other is on the fiber side.

Table 2: Young's modulus and Poisson ratio for the carbon-epoxy composite

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Poisson ratio
IM7 Carbon fiber	301	0.2
Epoxy resin	3.45	0.34

5-a

5-b

(5-c)

- 5-a The cross-section of the unidirectional reinforced composite
- 5-b The representative unit cell
- 5-c The finite element mesh of the unit cell

Fig.5: The Finite element model of the carbon-epoxy composite

(a) Radial and shear stress distribution along the interface
 (b) Normal stress distribution along the interface

Fig.6 Stress distribution along the interface

CONCLUSIONS

The heterogeneous element can be used not only for interfacial stress analysis of fibrous composites, but also for micro-stress analysis of all kinds of materials which are considered as micro-heterogeneous. Initial numerical results have shown that this heterogeneous element is an effective tool. Further research is needed to examine the convergent rate. More numerical data and comparisons are required to prove its reliability.

More complicated three-dimensional heterogeneous elements can be formulated in a similar manner. In addition, a heterogeneous element can also be formulated as a mixed and hybrid element. However, this is outside the scope of this paper. It will be discussed in a future publication.

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